

OLU-PREG[®] TEXTILE-BASED THERMOPLASTIC NCF-COMPOSITES

Frank Helbig^{1*}, Stefanie Schindler¹, Mike Scheika²

¹Technische Universität Chemnitz, Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Endowed Chair Textile Plastic Composites, D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany
Email: frank.helbig@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de/tkv/>

²SKM – Schwergewebe Konfektion Moers GmbH, Parsickstr. 39, D-47441 Moers, Germany
Email: scheika@skm-moers.com, web page: <http://skm-moers.com/de>

* Corresponding author (frank.helbig@mb.tu-chemnitz.de)

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ABSTRACT

Using the example of the non-crimp fabric (NCF) based OLU-Preg[®]-organic sheets consisting of continuous glass fibres and polypropylene, it is shown how by using glass fibre rovings with fineness of 600 tex and smaller, the mechanical properties of such textile reinforced plastics (TRP) can be purposefully influenced and improved. The textile technology development work has been focused on the provision of thermoplastic textile-reinforced composite materials that by varying the relevant component and process parameters on a large scale meet diverse and complex requirements profiles of modern TRP lightweight construction. In addition to the results of material investigations, the diversity of the structural design of OLU-Preg[®] composite semi-finished products and related design possibilities of textile-reinforced thin laminates are shown. In selected processing and application examples usability and possible uses of these NCF-based construction materials are outlined.

1 INTRODUCTION

Worldwide enormous efforts are being made to further improve the performance thermoplastic TRP while reducing production times and costs. The strength and stiffness of composite components is largely determined by the used textile reinforcement materials and structures and the fibre content and arrangements within the TRP. The thermoplastic TRP are due to their ductile material behaviour, the formability under thermal influence, short processing times and good recyclability the focus of material and process development for lightweight applications.

In addition to the micro and mesostructural arrangement of the textile reinforcing fibres, the maintenance of the structural order during the impregnation and consolidation process, as well as in forming under thermal stress regarding achievable composite benefits is quite essential in thermoplastic TRP materials. On the other hand, an impregnation of the textile reinforcement structures, due among other things to the higher viscosity of polymeric thermoplastic melts, is only possible over relatively short flow paths.

Complex textile semi-finished products are best suited to meet these particular requirements for the production and processing of thermoplastic TRP. They allow a targeted alignment already in the textile manufacturing process, for placing the matrix component accordingly in and around the structural order of the reinforcing fibres. Thus, easily manageable, structurally stable and drapable semi-finished products result, from which thermoplastic composites can be efficiently mass produced. Available textile technology and derived modifications provide technical and technological variants and ways to provide such complex semi-finished products for thermoplastic TRP.

Below are illustrated textile NCF semi-finished products produced using the laying technique, the way of processing them into new OLU-Preg[®] composites, selected properties of these novel thermoplastic TRP materials and various application possibilities.

2 MANUFACTURE OF THE OLU-PREG® - COMPOSITES

2.1 The textile-based composite semi-finished product

The basic textile structure consists of a multi-layer structure, in which unidirectionally aligned reinforcing fibre layers are wrapped on both sides in a likewise textile-based matrix material [1]. Since each composite component is assigned its own propagation plane in the layer structure, the semi-finished textile structure already contains mechanically independent reinforcement layers according to the design of uni directional (UD) laminates. The reinforcing fibre layers are formed by rovings of fineness of up to 600 tex. Particular means for spreading the reinforcing rovings in the installation process are completely eliminated.

Through the textile embedding of directly oriented NCF reinforcement layers, they are in the processing under pressure and temperature conditions for the impregnation mechanically protected and after the consolidation by a thin plastic coating they remain marcel free and structurally independent of one another. As a result, the reinforcement layers don't affect each other, whether as a semi-finished textile or composite, during further forming and reforming processes to adequate components. Rather, they can independently follow the forced changes in shape from direct orientation of the unidirectional single layer. Knitting yarns of compatible matrix material provide a secure connection between the individual sandwich layers in the manufacturing process into a composite.

The macrostructures and volume contents of the reinforcing fibre layers are determined by the roving fineness, the accumulation densities of the rovings in the laying process and the surface masses of the embedding textile matrix layers. Applying the large-series textile process for the manufacture of the multilayer structure all parameters can be varied in a wide range. The layer alternating arrangement consequences lead to short flow paths that need to be overcome by molten matrix in order to penetrate the reinforcing fibres.

Depending on the cut, the semi-finished product can be brought as a laminate to consolidation in any reinforcement direction, whether single or multilayered. This allows the manufacture in a processing step of load-capable laminates of up to 10 mm thickness, depending on the resulting minimum thickness of the basic layer structure from the varied ratio of reinforcing and matrix accumulation.

For the studies on the processing behaviour of textile-based composite semi-finished products and the resulting mechanical properties of the thermoplastic TRP OLU-Preg®, natural colored polypropylene (PP) as a matrix component was processed in combination with glass fibres (GF) in bidirectional 0° -90° orientation as a reinforcing component.

2.2 Structural variations and ways of processing

With the arbitrary amount of reinforcing fibre layers and quantities and the custom-fit coordination of the matrix mass ratios, structure arrangements equitable for special laminates can be produced with the OLU-Preg® technology already in the first production step, the textile manufacturing process, as double or multi-layer. Component and load-capable TRP semi-finished products are prefabricated this way by specifying more precise structural parameters with assignment of the required reinforcement directions. Size righteous cuts of the required reinforcement layers with the unidirectional NCF fibre orientations contained therein are combined to load adapted laminates. For the maximum degree of freedom of layer assignments in the laminate structure the OLU-Preg® as a single layer is available.

The textile-based OLU-Preg® semi-finished product exists as rolled goods regardless of the structural variants single, double or multi-layer. Differentiated further processing to fibre-reinforced composites can be derived herefrom. Both continuous and discontinuous manufacturing processes, for example in double belt presses and stationary presses for the manufacture of web-like thermoplastic TRP materials or TRP panels are applicable. This results in a two-stage process sequence to produce for example components through cold pressing out of the organic sheets present by the deforming and consolidating size righteous cut shapes.

The outstanding malleability of textile-based OLU-Preg[®] semi-finished products in connection with a thereby granted structural stability of the independent individual reinforcement layers also allows direct processing to complex component geometries in the single-stage hot pressing.

The growing demand for process-oriented and qualifying TRP semi-finished products can be satisfied with the provision of OLU-Preg[®] organic sheets, which were produced with the cold pressing method. A custom structure design to complex laminates is therefore paramount and offers within the textile technical and technological parameters spectrum enormous scope for component and application-oriented material developments.

2.3 Design, dimensioning, characteristic

The objective, providing thin-layered UD TRP materials, is connected in the technology-oriented structural design primarily with the establishment of and compliance with reproducible specific fibre volume contents (FVC). Following these demands, uniform accumulation distributions of TRP components in non-crimp fabrics were produced for textile-based OLU-Preg[®] composites with 40% and 50% FVC, using the available large-scale technology Malitronic[®] MULTIAXIAL. Among other things, the fineness of the reinforcing fibres were varied here and combined with matrix components in accordance with proportional mass.

The theoretical thicknesses of the detailed orthogonally reinforced OLU-Preg[®] composites can be calculated on the basis of the proportional component proportions. The smaller the deviation between theoretical and practical material thickness will be, the more certain can a good penetration of the reinforcing fibres with the matrix be. This form of confrontation allows exploratory assessment of the achieved processing quality in the fibre-reinforced plastic, although in this case the influence of a determined slight shrinkage of the matrix components is particularly neglected at the panel surfaces.

The degree of impregnation of the microstructural reinforcing fibres concerning the processing technology is connected with the composite specific target figure FVC and is thus also dependent on the porosity and permeability of the reinforcing structure. The assumed equal distribution of the composite components is affected in the textile manufacturing process of the macro-structural parameters roving fineness and laying density of the rovings.

In the case of a two-sided enclosure with the matrix components in the textile-based semi-finished product, the OLU-Preg[®] composites are characterised by smooth surfaces. The specially selected web structure with its evenly aligned directly oriented reinforcing structures leads to a full-scale, uniform fusion of the matrix component. A vertical break of the reinforcing fibres at the surfaces and the associated formation of craters are prevented by the vertical direction in mercel free fibre flows.

3 PROCESSING RESULTS AND CHARACTERISTICS

For the polypropylene (PP) glass fibres (GF)-OLU-Preg[®] composites as 0°-90° double layer with FVC of 40% result in the easy layers of material

- 0.2 mm material thickness at roving fineness of 150 tex,
- 0.4 mm material thickness at roving fineness of 300 tex,
- 0.8 mm material thickness at roving fineness of 600 tex.

The practically achieved thicknesses of the composites show good correlation with the theoretically determined values resulting from the assumption of a completely void and bubble-free compact accumulation of composite components. It was noted that in the same FVC of 40% and the same laying density of about 5 rovings/cm, the deviations of the nominal thickness of the theoretical material thicknesses are extremely low. Using 150 tex or 300 tex fine GF rovings the deviations are less than 1%, while at 600 tex fine rovings they are only 2%. With the selected laying densities better matrix penetration correlated with higher mechanical values was obtained, using the lower roving fineness (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Mechanical properties of PP-GF-OLU-Preg® composites (FVC = 40%)

Varying the textile parameters in the OLU-Preg® semi-finished product, the tensile strengths (R_m) as the primary criterion and the obtained tensile moduli as the secondary criterion were used as a basis for evaluating the composite performance. The specific tensile strength (R_s) leads to conclusions on the achieved substance use and the reached lightweight degree. Based on these studies, the parameters of the macro-structural arrangement of the reinforcement components were determined in terms of an efficient and resource-efficient production of the OLU-Preg® composites. As a result of the work, the material combinations based on 300 tex fine glass fibres were favoured.

Composition		Mechanical properties	
Matrix component	Polypropylen (PP)	Tensile strength	330 MPa
Reinforcing component	Glass fibre roving (GF), 300 tex	Tensile module	17.000 MPa
FVC	40 %	Elongation	2,5 %
Surface mass pro reinforcing layer	200 g/m ²	Bending strength	300 MPa
Number of reinforcing layers	2 (Double-Layer)	Bending module	20.000 MPa
TRP surface masses	625 g/m ²	Notched impact strength (Form C; -20°C)	340 kJ/m ²
TRP thickness	0,4 mm		

Table 1: NCF composite OLU-Preg® GB 400-40-1.10 (special product type); Composition and mechanical properties

With their single-layer only measuring 0.2 mm and the double-layer only 0.4 mm, the thin and smooth surfaced PP-GF organic sheets form an excellent basis for the production of thermoplastic thin-film laminates. The material properties of the NCF TRP based on the PP-GF-laminates from OLU-Preg® with 0°-90° reinforcement for FVC of totally 40% and equal amounts on each reinforcing direction with a total of 400 g/m² GF roving are shown in Table 1.

In the material tests dynamic tests were included. These were made based on the standardised bench test Falling-Dart. However, the samples in the available testing device could not be mounted on the supporting plate but laid out freely.

Fig. 2: Puncture sample, NCF-reinforced PP-GF-TRP

The NCF organic sheets were characterised by an energy absorption capacity similar to fabrics, withstanding the loads without showing any fragmentation at the puncture point (Fig. 2).

4 COMPONENT-ORIENTED PROCESSING AND APPLICATION

Custom designed OLU-Preg[®] thin-film laminates are used for example in the production of cold pressed thermoformed mouldings. The provision of organic sheets in areas of up to 2.5 m² and variable thicknesses based on thin individual layers can be employed both as a full reinforcement (Fig. 3) for thermoplastic TRP components as well as for extreme fibre or near-surface continuous fibre reinforcement for example in combination with GMT.

Fig. 3: Car underbody cover made of organic sheets

The particular material behaviour under strain, as it was observed even in the dynamic material testing, permits high forming degrees of therefore heated, plasticised OLU-Preg[®]-organic sheets in the shaping processes. Striking structural shifts within the individual reinforcement layers or structural inhibitions between them, leading to folds, can be reduced significantly or almost excluded by the use of the novel thermoplastic NCF composite compared to woven fabric-reinforced TRP materials. Arranged in separate layers, the directly oriented reinforcing fibres follow the form changes phase-independent. When sliding in their matrix embedding, the individual UD layers remain protected from the effects of the structural change of surrounding reinforcement layers in the laminate.

Plastics processing has increasingly set the goal of producing finished lightweight components requiring no post-processing, using TRP. Tremendous efforts are underway to qualify the injection moulding technologies to meet these objectives with regard to efficient and suitable for mass production plastic composite lightweight structures [2, 3].

Novel integrated component and manufacturing concepts are emerging that set high demands to the process, processing and performance of reinforcing semi-finished products such as organic sheets. The challenges for the realisation of the modern lightweight concept are the lowest possible installation space with maximum structural variability, especially in the composition to load-oriented laminates, thus resulting the smallest possible component masses at high material parameters, minimum restriction of deformability for maximum design flexibility of the construction elements.

In this research and development environment specialised OLU-Preg[®] composites were created and successfully brought for processing into the production processes of generally known demonstrators. The reinforcing fibres are only partially included into the matrix of the semi-finished product, lying on the surface flipped to the binding site of the injection moulding mass of the TRP semi-finished product to be cast.

The single-sided partially unbounded open reinforcing fibre content of the plasticised OLU-Preg[®] composites, that is formed when closing the cavity of the tool, can be penetrated by the injection moulded plastic and connected microstructurally beyond the plastic connection with the textile-based TRP component. The unbounded fibre components are quantified, that their complete penetration and connection with the injection moulded plastic can be expected [4].

For all further processing modes with additional plastic components, such as pressing with glass mat-reinforced thermoplastics (GMT) or fusing with injection moulded masses, the establishment of the components compatibility is a decisive criterion and guidance in the preparation of the OLU-Preg[®]-organic sheets.

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The OLU-Preg[®] technology makes novel construction materials that meet the diverse demands for mass reduction, structural variability, freedom of design and component and process compatibility available to custom-fit lightweight structures in the thermoplastic TRP segment. With the use of fibre rovings in low fineness TRP are formed, which manufactured as NCF with directly oriented reinforcing structures in highly productive textile process lead to large series reproducible, virtually recyclable material benefits. The produced load and component-adapted thermoplastic thin-film laminates show typical material behaviour of UD laminates. The significant effect of textile technical and technological parameters on the composite mechanical properties was detected and applied to optimise the process and product-oriented power delivery of OLU-Preg[®] organic sheets. In further work with the TU Chemnitz, the Endowed Chair “Textile Plastic Composites” practice-relevant combinations of composite components for the diversification of the OLU-Preg[®] technology and product spectrum are researched and developed.

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